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Navigating Challenges: Adversity Quotient, Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Strategies of Philippine National Police

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationships between adversity quotient (AQ), emotional intelligence (EI) and leadership strategies within organizational settings. A sample of 119 Philippine National Police Heads from diverse backgrounds and roles participated in the study. Descriptive-correlational design was used and data were collected using validated measures for EI, AQ, and leadership strategies. Data were statistically analyzed using SPSS and were interpreted at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed a “Low” level of adversity quotient of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz. A “High” level of emotional intelligence has emerged and a remarkable “High” level of leadership strategies had come forth. Generally, all of the socio-demographic profile being accounted for has conveyed no significant difference with regards to the level of adversity quotient, level of emotional intelligence and level of leadership strategies. However, there was a notable variation in the gender profile, namely in the adversity quotient level. Regardless of the characterization taken into account, the respondent's perspective does not vary. A significant positive relationship between EI and leadership strategies manifested indicating that individuals with higher levels of emotional intelligence were more likely to exhibit effective leadership behaviors and strategies. However, no significant relationship was observed between AQ and leadership strategies, suggesting that the ability to cope with adversity may not directly influence leadership effectiveness. These results underscore the importance of emotional intelligence in leadership development and organizational effectiveness. Organizations may benefit from prioritizing the cultivation of emotional intelligence skills among current and aspiring leaders to enhance leadership effectiveness and foster a positive organizational culture.

Keywords: *adversity quotient, emotional intelligence and leadership strategies*

Introduction

Life is full of challenges. In its different stages and slices. People meet and encounter hardships, challenges, adversities and sorrows which are varying to bridge in all endeavors. There would come an instance that an individual would be putting himself into a trial and situation that would test to determine the length of his patience, his strength to overcome it, his wisdom to make the wisest decision, and his logic to put things in proper perspective and in the end to learn something out of this situation. This maybe the best time to know if that person would meet another problem, can figure out his capacity to overcome himself in the easiest and most effective way.

Nowadays, the law enforcement community faces varied and daily challenges that cause stress that few of the other professions understand. Facing many issues and emerging adversities with which the law enforcers leaders must contend. They are often forced to deal with recurrent internal and external problems in their operation. How these problems are resolved is highly dependent upon the station chief of police and all unit heads along with their personal qualities to express their styles of leadership and management abilities.

According to a study of police shift work, “Few occupations require the intensity of constant alertness, proper mood and demeanor, short term memory, and physiological stamina that police work requires.” To be an effective and efficient law enforcement officer in today’s environment requires intelligence about and control of emotions to meet the demands faced on the streets. Today’s officers need to be highly motivated; have well developed communication skills; and be able to engage leadership, other officers, and community members by managing relationships and making emotional connections to balance the needs of the organization and the community.

This study is challenged to relate the principles of adversity quotient of Dr. Stoltz (1997) and Emotional Intelligence of Goleman to the law enforcement community being the workplace of the police personnel. Essential information were gathered in this study to help discover the hidden resource that could spell out success or failure in the leadership of Philippine National Police.

Through this study, the researcher would be able to determine the navigating challenges in terms of adversity quotient, emotional intelligence and leadership strategies of Philippine National Police Heads.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this study was to determine the navigating challenges in terms of adversity quotient, emotional intelligence and leadership strategies of Philippine National Police Heads. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?

2. What is the level of adversity quotient of Philippine National Police Heads as a whole and in terms of control, ownership, reach and endurance?
3. What is the level of emotional intelligence of Philippine National Police Heads as a whole and in terms of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management?
4. What is the level of leadership strategies of Philippine National Police Heads as a whole and in terms of autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of adversity quotient of Philippine National Police heads when they are grouped according to their demographic profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of emotional intelligence of Philippine National Police heads when they are grouped according to their demographic profile?
7. Is there a significant difference in the level of leadership strategies of Philippine National Police heads when they are grouped according to their demographic profile?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the level of adversity quotient and level of leadership strategies of Philippine National Police Heads?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the level of emotional intelligence and level of leadership strategies of Philippine National Police heads?
10. Is there a significant relationship between the adversity quotient and emotional intelligence of Philippine National Police Heads?
11. What output can be drawn from the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design utilized for this study was the descriptive-correlational research to determine the adversity quotient, emotional intelligence and leadership strategies of PNP heads. This design is concerned with the conditions or relationship that exist, practices that prevail, point of view or attitude that are held, and practices that are developing. It is often combined with comparison or contrast involving measurement and interpretation. According to Fraenkel and Wallen (1993), correlational research is done to determine relationship among two or more variables and to explore their implications for cause and effect. According to Adedoyin (2020), quantitative research is research directed at the study of a certain phenomenon using numerical data interpreted using statistical, analytical, or computing tools. Furthermore, quantitative research has a positivist paradigm that allows for approaches in which statistical data is involved, such as inferential statistics, experimental and quasi-experimental design randomization, etc. And which questionnaires are restricted in their predefined answers (Lee, as cited in Slevitch, 2011)

Descriptive method proceeds to describe certain phenomena. For this reason, some authorities in research describe it to be fact finding or information gathering with analytical interpretations. In the words of Best (1989): The descriptive method concerns with conditions or relationships that exist; practices that prevail; beliefs and processes that are going on; effects that are being felt or trends that are developing.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the fourteen (14) chief of police and one hundred five (105) unit heads in the sixteen (16) municipal police stations and one (1) city police station in the province of Capiz.

The distribution of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution of respondents*

<i>Location</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Dao	10	7	5.88
Cuartero	10	7	5.88
Dumalag	10	7	5.88
Dumarao	10	7	5.88
Ivisan	10	7	5.88
Jamindan	10	7	5.88
Maayon	10	7	5.88
Mambusao	10	7	5.88
Panay	10	7	5.88
Pilar	10	7	5.88
Panit-An	10	7	5.88
Pontevedra	10	7	5.88
President Roxas	10	7	5.88
Sapian	10	7	5.88
Sigma	10	7	5.88
Roxas City	10	7	5.88

Tapaz	10	7	5.88
Total	170	119	100

Instrument

For the instrument to be considered valid, it was submitted for content validation. Content validity is the degree to which the items in the questionnaire represent the essence, the topics and the areas that the test is designed to measure. Content validity is the most crucial procedure because it sets the pace for the succeeding validity and reliability means. Each member of the committee would validate the items in the questionnaire by way of reading each statement and assessed whether or not the items were appropriate for the study. Questionnaire Reliability was pretested in Passi City.

The questionnaire consisted of three parts. Part one dealt with the personal information about the respondents such as their name (optional), sex, age, marital status, , designation, length of service and educational attainment.

Part two, dealt with the level of adversity quotient of the PNP heads in the Province of Capiz with a reliability score of .895

Part three, dealt with the level of emotional intelligence of the PNP heads in the Province of Capiz with a reliability score .848

Lastly, part three focused on the leadership strategies of the PNP heads in the Province of Capiz with reliability score of .853.

Procedure

The researcher took the number and list of police heads in the province of Capiz. Letter request was then secured from the graduate school addressed to the Municipal Chief of Police asking for an approval to conduct the study within the municipal stations uniformed personnel. When the letter was granted, the researcher personally distributed the copies of the reproduced data gathering instruments. After retrieval of the questionnaire, they were encoded and tallied. These were fed to IM Statistical Package for Social and Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis

The study used the following statistical tools and techniques:

Frequencies and Percentage. These were used in determining the profiles of the respondents in terms of demographic variables (age, sex, marital status, designation, educational attainment and length of service), adversity quotient, emotional intelligence and leadership strategies.

t-test Independent and One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). These were utilized in determining significant differences specifically the grouping of respondents considering the independent variables included in this study.

Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlational. It was used to determine if there was a significant relationship between adversity quotient and emotional intelligence, adversity quotient and leadership strategies and emotional intelligence and leadership strategies.

The level of significance was set at .05 alpha.

Results and Discussion

The gathered data were presented, examined, and explained in this chapter. The presentation is carried out according to the order in which each research question needs to be addressed.

Socio- Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The sociodemographic profile of the one hundred nineteen (119) respondents, who were various chiefs and department heads of the Philippine National Police in the Province of Capiz, taken into consideration for this study was displayed in Table Two (2). These profiles included: gender, age, marital status, designation, educational attainment, and length of service.

Gender. Majority of the respondents, 66 (55.5%) were males and 45 (37.8%) were females, there were a few 8 (6.7%) who preferred not to divulge their genders.

Age. Most, 53 (44.5%) of the respondents were in the age bracket of 28-37 years old, a little closer 47 (39.5%) were aged 38-47 years old, an eighth (12.6%) were in the age range of 48-57 years old, and the smallest in percentage were aged 48-57 years old and above as well as 27 years old and below both with 2 (1.7%) for each age groups.

Marital Status. In terms of the civil status of the respondents, almost three quarters 87 (73.1%) were married, 27 (22.7%) were single and a few 5 (4.2%) were already widowed.

Designation. Three (3) positions composed the three-fifths of the total respondents with nearly a fifth 23 (19.3%) each of the following positions: Chiefs of Administration & Logistics, Chiefs of Operation and Finance, and Chiefs of Intel and Investigation. Middling the pack, at a little over a tenth 14 (11.8%) were Chiefs of Police of various stations. Another three (3) positions with equally a tenth 12 (10.1%) of the total population were: Chiefs for WCPD (Women and Children Protection Desk), Chiefs for Community Relations, and

the Chiefs for Traffic.

Educational Attainment. Dominantly 104 (87.4%) among the respondents were bachelor’s degree holder, a little 8 (6.7%) had their master’s degree, a few 5 (4.2%) currently having their master’s units, 1 (0.8%) respondent each with doctoral degree and having doctoral units.

Length of Service. In terms of the respondent’s tenure at work, primarily 86 (72.3%) had served the police force for at least 11 years and above, the rest with a little over a quarter 33 (27.7%) of the total responders had served for 4-10 years.

Table 2. Socio-demographic profile of the respondents

Profile / Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	66	55.5%
	Female	45	37.8%
	Prefer Not to Say	8	6.7%
	Total:	119	100%
Age	58 years old and above	2	1.7%
	48-57 years old	15	12.6%
	38-47 years old	47	39.5%
	28-37 years old	53	44.5%
	27 years old below	2	1.7%
	Total:	119	100%
Marital Status	Single	27	22.7%
	Married	87	73.1%
	Widowed	5	4.2%
	Total:	119	100%
Designation	Chief of Police	14	11.8%
	Chief of Administration & Logistics	23	19.3%
	Chief of Operation and Finance	23	19.3%
	Chief of Intel and Investigation	23	19.3%
	Chief for WCPD	12	10.1%
	Chief for Community Relation	12	10.1%
	Chief for Traffic	12	10.1%
	Total:	119	100%
	Educational Attainment	Bachelor’s Degree	104
With Master’s Degree Units		5	4.2%
Master’s Degree		8	6.7%
With Doctoral Units		1	0.8%
Doctorate Degree		1	0.8%
Total:		119	100%
Length of Service	11 years and above	86	72.3%
	4-10 years	33	27.7%
	Total:	119	100%

Level of Adversity Quotient of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz

Presented in Table 3 was the level of adversity quotient of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz.

Table 3. Level of adversity quotient of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Control: To what extent can you influence the situation?		
1. You suffer a financial setback.	2.73	Average
2. People respond unfavorably to your latest ideas.	2.49	Low
3. You are not exercising regularly though you know you should.	2.21	Low
4. Your personal and work obligations are out of balance.	2.07	Low
5. Your computer crashed the third time this week.	1.85	Low
Average Mean:	2.27	Low
Ownership: To what extent do you hold yourself responsible for improving this situation?		
1. You are overlooked for a promotion.	2.35	Low
2. Your workplace is understaffed.	2.24	Low
3. Someone you respect ignores your attempt to discuss an important issue.	1.96	Low
4. Your organization is not meeting its goals.	1.82	Low
5. The meeting you are is a total waste of time.	1.66	Very Low
Average Mean:	2.01	Low
Reach: How far does the fallout of this situation reach into other areas of your work or life?		
1. You are criticized for a big project that you just completed.	1.92	Low

2. You hit every red light on your way to an important appointment.	1.87	Low
3. Your boss adamantly disagrees with your decision.	1.84	Low
4. You miss an important appointment	1.76	Very Low
5. The high priority project you are working on gets canceled.	1.71	Very Low
Average Mean:	1.82	Low
Endurance: How long will the adversity endure?		
1. You never seem to have enough money.	2.26	Low
2. You are unable to take a much-needed vacation.	2.41	Low
3. After extensive searching, you cannot find an important document.	1.99	Low
4. You lost something that is important to you.	1.94	Low
5. You accidentally deleted an important email.	1.59	Very Low
Average Mean:	2.04	Low
Grand Mean:	2.03	Low

Scale: 4.21–5.00 Very High | 3.41–4.20 High | 2.61–3.40 Average | 1.81–2.60 Low | 1.00–1.80 Very Low

These identified adversities have been classified into four (4) categories, namely: Control – the extent of influence in the situation; Ownership – the extent of holding oneself being responsible to improve the situation; Reach – the scope the situation reaches into areas of your work or life; and Endurance – the persistence to endure adversity.

The adversity quotient was generally rated by the respondents at a “Low” level with a grand mean score of 2.03. With all of its facets having all “Low” level ratings as well.

In terms of Control, it had been scored at 2.27 “Low” level, Endurance has 2.03 “Low” level rating, the Ownership aspect was rated with a “Low” level at a mean rating of 2.01, and Reach at a “Low” level rating of 1.82 mean score.

A low adversity quotient scores implies that the members of the institution is more likely to struggle in difficult situations and that the situation has a negative impact on them. A person with low AQ is more susceptible to mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, or other physical health problems.

One must adjust its response if hardship and disagreeable difficulties quickly depress you. Take charge of the matter and be responsible. It is normal to experience failure sometimes. Develop new skills and perspective, these can help oneself to become stronger and more resilient.

Level of Emotional Intelligence of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz

Displayed in Table 4 is the level of emotional intelligence of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz. The statements were grouped into four (4) areas: Self-Awareness, Self-Management, Social Awareness, and Relationship Management. Overall, the respondent’s emotional intelligence has highly fared at 3.94 “High” level rating.

Self-Management scored “High” level at a mean rating of 4.15, with a “Very High” level scores particularly in the statements: “During changing situations, I always work hard to try and keep up with the demands (M=4.25)” and “When I am under pressure, I think clearly and stay focus (M=4.24). Relationship Management also managed a “High” level rating at a mean score of 4.11, same as with the Social Awareness with 3.88 “High” level rating as well as with the Self-Awareness with 3.64 mean score at a “High” degree.

Having a high Emotional Quotient facilitates relationship building, lowers team stress, diffuses conflict, and increases job satisfaction. Emotionally intelligent persons are said to be able to adapt their behavior and thought processes to fit the situation or to accomplish specific objectives. In the end, having a high EI indicates the capacity to boost team output and employee retention.

Table 4. *Level of emotional intelligence of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz*

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Self-Awareness		
1. I always like to take on new challenges.	4.00	High
2. Where there are uncertainties and pressures, I am always cautious about making the right decision.	3.81	High
3. I generally have a good sense of humor about myself.	3.76	High
4. When I am under pressure, I generally have behaviors that remain unchanged.	3.39	Average
5. My emotions generally have a strong impact on the way I behave.	3.23	Average
Average Mean:	3.64	High
Self-Management		
1. During changing situations, I always work hard to try and keep up with the demands.	4.25	Very High
2. When I am under pressure, I think clearly and stay focused.	4.24	Very High
3. Generally, I pursue goals beyond what is required or expected of me.	4.18	High
4. When obstacles and setbacks occur in pursuing my goals, I always persist in seeking the goals despite what has happened.	4.17	High
5. I generally keep my disruptive emotions and impulses under control.	3.92	High
Average Mean:	4.15	High
Social Awareness		

1. I always find social networks in the organization help create better decision networks.	4.00	High
2. I always use formal decision networks to get what I need.	3.97	High
3. I always help out based on understanding others' needs and feelings.	3.92	High
4. Others perspective is always understood and sensitivity shown.	3.91	High
5. When I see bias and intolerance, I always challenge the initiating people.	3.60	High
Average Mean:	3.88	High
Relationship Management		
1. I always communicate in a way that everyone understands what I am saying	4.32	Very High
2. I generally have a balanced focus on tasks and relationships.	4.26	Very High
3. When I work with teams, I always make it clear what I expect members to do.	4.24	Very High
4. I always give assignments to people who will grow and develop as a result of the challenge.	3.98	High
5. Winning people over is something that I find difficult to do.	3.73	High
Average Mean:	4.11	High
Grand Mean:	3.94	High

Scale: 4.21–5.00 Very High | 3.41–4.20 High | 2.61–3.40 Average | 1.81–2.60 Low | 1.00–1.80 Very Low

Level of Leadership Strategies of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz

Exhibited in 5 is the level of leadership strategies of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz.

Leadership strategies were classified into three: the Autocratic type or the authoritarian; Democratic or the participative type of leadership; and the Laissez-Faire or the Delegative type.

The level of leadership strategies was appraised by the respondents to be in a “High” degree, with grand mean score of 4.04. Democratic type of leadership scored a “Very High” level with a mean rating of 4.40. Consultation with subordinates and taking into account their opinions and suggestions when making decisions are hallmarks of democratic leadership. Democratic leaders often think that everyone should have a voice in decision-making and have a great deal of respect for their subordinates.

Laissez-Faire type of leadership got a 4.16 “High” level score. In this style of leadership, it empowers the staff freedom and having faith in them to complete the task without micromanaging them. While being accessible to offer criticism as needed, laissez-faire leaders leave to their staff the decision in making judgments.

Autocratic type of leadership with mean score of 3.55 “High” level rating. This type of leadership entails the leader giving all commands and making all of the decisions. Leaders that exhibit autocratic tendencies typically possess a strong hold on their subordinates and aren't hesitant to utilize their power to accomplish tasks.

Having a strong leadership plan, it will be simpler to manage teams, assign tasks, and it promotes a collaborative work environment. Leaders will enable qualitative changes within the team, from managing expectations and engaging staff to increasing their productivity.

Table 5. Level of leadership strategies of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Autocratic (Authoritarian)		
1. I directly supervised my personnel in order to achieve the organizational goals/objectives	4.23	Very High
2. I closely monitor my personnel if they are performing their job correctly.	4.20	High
3. I always make and retain the final decision making as the head of the station/unit.	3.76	High
4. I do not listen to my subordinates if they justify a situation wrongly.	3.00	Average
5. I carry out decisions without consulting the group.	2.54	Low
Average Mean:	3.55	High
Democratic (Participative)		
7. I encourage my personnel to participate in decision making.	4.49	Very High
8. I assign duties during planning period and deliberate it accordingly.	4.44	Very High
9. I remain calm when uncertain things come and resolve it through the optimum participation of everybody.	4.38	Very High
6. I like to share my leadership power with my subordinates.	4.35	Very High
10. I call a meeting to get my personnel's opinion to create a strategy on a project or on a process running.	4.34	Very High
Average Mean:	4.40	Very High
Laissez-Faire (Delegative)		
1. I encourage my personnel to use their creativity and ingenuity to solve organizational problems	4.34	Very High
2. I delegate responsibility to enhance the ability and potential of my subordinates.	4.29	Very High
3. I delegate to my personnel the ideas and inputs on upcoming plans and projects for the station.	4.14	High
4. I hold my subordinates accountable on every detail of work assigned to them.	4.09	High
5. I assigned the task and let my personnel handle it by themselves.	3.96	High
Average Mean:	4.16	High
Grand Mean:	4.04	High

Scale: 4.21–5.00 Very High | 3.41–4.20 High | 2.61–3.40 Average | 1.81–2.60 Low | 1.00–1.80 Very Low

To establish the significant difference within the compared variables, the scores from the gathered data of the compared variables were tested using ANOVA or Independent Samples test, the values of F or t, the sig-value and description which determines if the variable or the profile is significantly different.

Significant Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of PNP Heads in Terms of Selected Profile

To determine the significant difference in the level of adversity quotient of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz in terms of selected socio-demographic profiles, succeeding table (Table 6) shows the results.

Among all the chosen socio-demographic characteristics as compared to the level of adversity quotient, the only profile with a distinct significant difference was with the respondent's gender. With the outcome of the F-value=5.977 and sig-value=0.003 which was highly significant at 0.05 alpha. Point of view of different sexes varies in their perception of the adversity level.

All other profiles such as age, marital status, designation, educational attainment, length of service, all of these exhibited a no significant difference when all these profiles have been taken into consideration. Results of the sig-value as shown on Table 6 were all beyond the 0.05 significance level.

Factors of any of these demographic profile does not affect the respondent's standpoint when it comes to the effect of adversities on them. The result of the study was not similar to that study of Calusor (2022) where respondents are dominated by male police officers but showed no significant differences in facing adversities.

Table 6. Significant difference in the level of adversity quotient of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz in terms of gender, age, marital status, designation, educational attainment and length of service

Compared Variable	Mean	F-value	Sig-value	Remarks	
Gender:					
Male	2.05	5.977	0.003	Significant	
Female	1.87				
Prefer Not to Say	2.84				
Age:					
58 years old and above	1.85	0.137	0.968	Not Significant	
48-57 years old	1.95				
38-47 years old	2.06				
28-37 years old	2.03				
27 years old below	2.30				
Marital Status:					
Single	2.03	0.106	0.899	Not Significant	
Married	2.04				
Widowed	1.88				
Designation:					
Chief of Police	1.82	1.438	0.206	Not Significant	
Chief of Administration & Logistics	2.01				
Chief of Operation and Finance	1.84				
Chief of Intel and Investigation	2.32				
Chief for WCPD	1.93				
Chief for Community Relation	1.93				
Chief for Traffic	2.36				
Educational Attainment:					
Bachelor's Degree	2.06	0.704	0.591		Not Significant
With Master's Degree Units	1.56				
Master's Degree	1.89				
With Doctoral Units	2.45				
Doctorate Degree	2.40				
Length of Service:					
11 years and above	2.09	1.216	0.227	Not Significant	
4-10 years	1.90				

$\alpha = 0.05$

Significant Difference in the Level of Emotional Intelligence of PNP Heads in Terms of Selected Profile

Table 7 displays the significant difference in the level of emotional intelligence of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz in terms of selected socio-demographic profiles.

All of the considered profiles, which included gender, age, marital status, designation, educational attainment, and length of service, these all has no occurrence of a significant difference when put into consideration and being compared in terms of the level of emotional intelligence.

Values of the results of the F-value and sig-value as displayed on Table 7 were all evident to be far away from the value of significant level set at 0.05 alpha. Thus, all null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the respondent's conception of the level of emotional intelligence in terms of the selected profiles were all not rejected.

Regardless of any of the characterization considered, the respondent's impression towards the level of emotional intelligence does not differ. It implies that emotional intelligence is a trait that is not inherently tied to any particular demographic characteristic. People from various backgrounds and demographics can possess similar levels of emotional intelligence. Additionally, if emotional intelligence is not affected by demographic factors, it underscores the importance of creating inclusive environments where individuals from all backgrounds can thrive.

The result of the study was differed to that study of Agbor et.al (2014) about the Emotional intelligence where males had higher emotional intelligence as compare to females and found significant gender differences in emotional intelligence among police personnel.

Table 7. Significant difference in the level of emotional intelligence of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz in terms of gender, age, marital status, designation, educational attainment and length of service

	Compared Variable	Mean	F-value	Sig-value	Remarks
Gender:	Male	3.87	0.820	0.443	Not Significant
	Female	4.04			
	Prefer Not to Say	4.08			
Age:	58 years old and above	4.20	0.604	0.661	Not Significant
	48-57 years old	4.13			
	38-47 years old	3.83			
	28-37 years old	3.99			
	27 years old below	3.95			
Marital Status:	Single	3.88	0.372	0.690	Not Significant
	Married	3.95			
	Widowed	4.19			
Designation:	Chief of Police	4.16	1.024	0.413	Not Significant
	Chief of Administration & Logistics	3.84			
	Chief of Operation and Finance	4.00			
	Chief of Intel and Investigation	3.67			
	Chief for WCPD	4.01			
	Chief for Community Relation	4.20			
	Chief for Traffic	3.99			
Educational Attainment:	Bachelor's Degree	3.91	0.609	0.657	Not Significant
	With Master's Degree Units	4.20			
	Master's Degree	4.07			
	With Doctoral Units	4.85			
	Doctorate Degree	4.15			
Length of Service:	11 years and above	3.90	-1.088	0.279	Not Significant
	4-10 years	4.07			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Significant Difference in the Level of Leadership Strategies of PNP Heads in Terms of Selected Profile

Illustrated in table 8 below were the significant difference of the level of leadership strategies of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz according to the chosen socio-demographic factors.

When evaluated in terms of the degree of leadership techniques, there is no discernible difference between any of the profiles that were taken into consideration, including gender, age, marital status, designation, level of education attained, and duration of service.

Statistical outcomes of the scores of the F-value and sig-value shows no significant difference among any variable put into consideration with respect to the level of leadership strategies. This suggests not to reject the null hypothesis of no difference among the compared variables.

The respondent's assessment of the degree of the leadership strategies is the same regardless of any of the descriptors taken into consideration.

The finding supports the idea of a meritocratic approach to leadership, wherein individuals are evaluated and promoted based on their abilities and skills rather than demographic attributes. It suggests that successful leadership is more about the competencies and strategies employed rather than demographic traits.

Although there may not be significant differences in the level of leadership strategies across demographics, it's important to recognize that individuals may still exhibit diverse leadership styles based on their unique personalities, experiences, and preferences. Embracing this diversity can enrich organizational leadership and foster innovation and creativity.

Table 8. Significant difference in the level of leadership strategies of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz in terms of gender, age, marital status, designation, educational attainment and length of service

Compared Variable	Mean	F-value	Sig-value	Remarks
Gender:				
Male	4.04	1.040	0.357	Not Significant
Female	3.97			
Prefer Not to Say	4.37			
Age:				
58 years old and above	4.66	0.665	0.617	Not Significant
48-57 years old	4.14			
38-47 years old	4.04			
28-37 years old	4.00			
27 years old below	3.56			
Marital Status:				
Single	3.82	1.694	0.188	Not Significant
Married	4.11			
Widowed	3.99			
Designation:				
Chief of Police	4.14	0.199	0.977	Not Significant
Chief of Administration & Logistics	3.93			
Chief of Operation and Finance	4.00			
Chief of Intel and Investigation	4.03			
Chief for WCPD	4.10			
Chief for Community Relation	4.16			
Chief for Traffic	4.03			
Educational Attainment:				
Bachelor's Degree	4.01	1.072	0.374	Not Significant
With Master's Degree Units	3.75			
Master's Degree	4.39			
With Doctoral Units	4.73			
Doctorate Degree	4.60			
Length of Service:				
11 years and above	4.05	0.268	0.789	Not Significant
4-10 years	4.01			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Significant Relationships Between the Level of Adversity Quotient and Level of Leadership Strategies of the PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz

Table 9 presents the correlation scrutiny between the level of adversity quotient and level of leadership strategies of various PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz.

According to Table 9 the overall result of $r = -0.020$ and $\text{sig-value} = 0.829$ which was not significant in reference to 0.05 alpha. The result indicates that there is no relationship among the two variables compared. The level of adversity quotient has nothing to do directly with the level of leadership strategies.

The findings also suggests that leaders do not significantly alter their strategies based on the level of adversity they face. This could indicate that effective leaders maintain a consistent approach to leadership regardless of the challenges they encounter, demonstrating adaptability and resilience in their leadership style.

Table 9. *Significant relationships between the level of adversity quotient and level of leadership strategies of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz*

Compared Variable	r-value	Sig-value	Remarks
Level of Adversity Quotient	-0.020	0.829	Not Significant
Level of Leadership Strategies			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Significant Relationships Between the Level of Emotional Intelligence and Level of Leadership Strategies of the PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz

Table 10 provides the association analysis between the level of emotional intelligence and level of leadership strategies of various PNP heads in the Province of Capiz.

In reference to Table 11, the outcome of $r = 0.621$ and $\text{sig-value} = 0.000$ which was highly significant in reference to 0.05 alpha. The result indicates that there is indeed a relationship among the two variables compared. The level of emotional intelligence and level of leadership strategies, in some ways, has a relevant effect with each other.

The finding connotes that individuals with higher levels of emotional intelligence are more likely to employ effective leadership strategies. Emotional intelligence encompasses skills such as self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and social skills, which are crucial for effective leadership. Leaders who possess high emotional intelligence may be better equipped to understand and manage their own emotions as well as those of others, leading to more effective leadership behaviors and strategies. Leaders with higher emotional intelligence may be more adaptable and flexible in their approach to leadership. They may be able to assess the emotional needs of their team members and adjust their strategies accordingly to inspire, motivate, and support them effectively, particularly in challenging or changing situations.

Table 10. *Significant relationships between the level of emotional intelligence and level of leadership strategies of PNP heads in the Province of Capiz*

Compared Variable	r-value	Sig-value	Remarks
Level of Emotional Intelligence		0.000	Significant
Level of leadership Strategies			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Significant Relationships Between the Level of Adversity Quotient and Level of Emotional Intelligence of the PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz

Table 11 exhibits the correlation comparison between the level of adversity quotient and level of emotional intelligence of various PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz.

Per Table 11 the results of $r = -0.109$ and $\text{sig-value} = 0.239$ which was not significant in regards to the significant level set to 0.05 alpha. The outcome shows that the two variables under comparison have no association. The level of adversity quotient and level of emotional intelligence of various PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz, as correlated together, has no substantial connection between them.

The absence of a relationship suggests that AQ and EI are distinct constructs that measure different aspects of an individual's psychological makeup. Adversity quotient primarily focuses on an individual's ability to cope with and overcome adversity, while emotional intelligence relates to one's ability to perceive, understand, and manage emotions in oneself and others.

Table 11. *Significant relationships between the level of adversity quotient and level of emotional intelligence of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz*

Compared Variable	r-value	Sig-value	Remarks
Level of Adversity Quotient	-0.109	0.239	Not Significant
Level of Emotional Intelligence			

$\alpha = 0.05$

Proposed Training Programs to Enhance Adversity Quotient and Emotional Intelligence in the Philippine National Police

The Philippine National Police (PNP) operates in an environment characterized by high stress, unpredictability, and a continuous demand for effective leadership and decision-making. To navigate these challenges and to ensure optimal performance, it is imperative that police personnel, especially those in leadership roles, possess strong Adversity Quotient (AQ) and Emotional Intelligence (EI).

Adversity Quotient is a measure of an individual's resilience and ability to thrive in the face of challenges. In the context of law enforcement, a high AQ enables officers to handle stress, recover from setbacks, and maintain composure in difficult situations.

Emotional Intelligence (EI): Emotional Intelligence refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions, as

well as the emotions of others. For PNP personnel, high EI is critical for effective leadership, conflict resolution, and fostering a positive work environment.

The proposed training programs aim to enhance the Adversity Quotient (AQ) and Emotional Intelligence (EI) of the Philippine National Police (PNP) personnel. These programs are crucial for fostering resilience, improving stress management, and enhancing problem-solving abilities. By developing high AQ, officers will be better equipped to handle challenges and adversity in their professional and personal lives. Additionally, improving EI will enhance interpersonal skills, effective communication, and conflict resolution, contributing to a positive and productive work environment. Ultimately, these programs will lead to more competent and emotionally resilient police officers, thereby improving overall organizational performance and public service.

Implementing training programs focused on enhancing Adversity Quotient and Emotional Intelligence within the PNP is a strategic initiative that addresses the critical needs of the organization. By investing in the personal and professional development of its personnel, the PNP will not only improve the effectiveness and efficiency of its operations but also foster a healthier, more resilient, and emotionally intelligent workforce capable of meeting the challenges of modern policing.

Conclusions

The results and findings presented above lead to the following conclusions:

A “Low” level of adversity quotient of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz has occurred as regarded by the respondents. A low adversity quotient score suggests that the institution's members are more likely to experience negative effects from challenging circumstances and to struggle in such circumstances. One needs to adjust their response to adversity and unfavorable challenges, take responsibility, and take control of the situation. Develop new perspectives and abilities, these will make you stronger and more resilient.

A “High” level of emotional intelligence of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz had emerged. By having a high emotional quotient building relationships is facilitated, team tension is reduced, conflict is diffused, and job satisfaction is raised. People who possess emotional intelligence are believed to be able to shift their behavior and ways of thinking to suit the circumstances or to achieve particular goals. A high EI suggests the ability to increase team productivity and employee retention.

A “High” level of leadership strategies of PNP Heads in the Province of Capiz had come forth. Having an excellent leadership strategy makes it easier to delegate tasks, manage teams, and fosters a collaborative work atmosphere. Leaders will facilitate qualitative changes in the team, from raising productivity to managing expectations and empowering employees.

Generally, all of the socio-demographic profile being accounted for had conveyed no significant difference with regards to the level of adversity quotient, level of emotional intelligence and level of leadership strategies. There is no appreciable difference between any of the profiles that were taken into consideration including gender, age, marital status, designation, educational attainment, and length of service. With the only exception with the gender's profile particularly with the level of adversity quotient has the occurrence of a significant difference. The respondent's perception remains unchanged, regardless of the characterization taken into consideration.

Effective leaders may demonstrate resilience in the face of adversity by maintaining their leadership strategies despite challenging circumstances. This resilience could stem from their confidence in their abilities, their commitment to their vision and values, or their belief in the effectiveness of their chosen strategies.

While overall levels of emotional intelligence may not differ significantly across demographics, there may still be specific groups or individuals who could benefit from targeted interventions. Identifying such groups and tailoring interventions accordingly could lead to more effective outcomes.

Since no difference was noted in the leadership strategies when selected profiles was taken into account, organizations can use this understanding to design more inclusive and effective leadership development programs that cater to the diverse needs and backgrounds of the individual. By focusing on developing leadership competencies rather than targeting specific demographic groups, these programs can better prepare individuals for leadership roles.

Since no relationship was noted between adversity quotient and leadership strategies this could mean that the findings underscores the importance of leadership competencies and skills in navigating challenging situations. Leaders who possess a strong skill set and understanding of effective leadership principles may be better equipped to maintain their strategies in the face of adversity, regardless of external factors.

A high significant relationship manifested between emotional intelligence and leadership strategies would imply that emotional intelligence is closely linked to effective communication and relationship-building skills. Leaders with higher emotional intelligence may be more adept at fostering positive relationships, resolving conflicts, and building trust within their teams, all of which are essential for successful leadership.

While no overall relationship may exist between AQ and EI, there may still be individual differences in how these traits interact or manifest in specific contexts. Some individuals may naturally excel in both areas, while others may demonstrate strengths in one domain over the other.

Based on the findings and conclusions cited from the study, the following recommendations were hereby recommended:

Training and Development Program. Since the Adversity Quotient of police personnel heads in the province of Capiz was found to be low, the Department of Local and Interior Government may implement training programs focused on developing resilience skills, such as stress management, problem-solving, and emotional regulation. They should offer workshops, seminars, or online courses that provide practical strategies for overcoming adversity and building mental toughness,

Promote Collaboration and Teamwork. The Police organization may encourage individuals with high EI to collaborate with others and leverage their interpersonal skills to foster strong relationships and build cohesive teams. Emphasize the importance of effective communication, active listening, and conflict resolution in creating a positive and productive work environment.

Recognition and Empowerment. The Government, specifically the Department of Interior and Local Government, may recognize and empower individuals with high leadership strategies by entrusting them with greater responsibility and autonomy. They may acknowledge their contributions to the organization and provide opportunities for them to take on leadership roles in key projects or initiatives.

Consistency in Leadership and Management Practices. The Chief of Police should ensure consistency and uniformity across profiles, as this may indicate that leadership and management practices are applied consistently throughout the organization. This suggests that leaders and managers follow standardized procedures and approaches in decision-making, communication, and performance management, promoting fairness and predictability.

Unique Assessment Measures. The PNP Organization as a whole may need to use different assessment measures to evaluate individuals' proficiency in AQ, leadership strategies, and emotional intelligence. By using specialized assessment tools tailored to each construct, organizations can obtain a more comprehensive understanding of individuals' strengths and areas for growth, enabling targeted development efforts.

Future research may explore additional factors that may influence leadership strategies and further investigate the complex interplay between emotional intelligence, adversity quotient, and leadership effectiveness within diverse organizational contexts.

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